

INVESTMENT ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation *The article describes the basics of investment activities in Uzbekistan, the purposes of use, the types of investments according to the sources of financing. The article discusses some aspects of the implementation of investment activities by legal entities and individuals in the republic.*

Key words: *investment, investor, investment activity, property, project, subjects of investment activity, investment resources, capital investment, innovative investment, social investment.*

Аннотация *В статье описаны основы инвестиционной деятельности в Узбекистане, цели использования, виды инвестиций по источникам финансирования. В статье рассмотрены некоторые аспекты осуществления инвестиционной деятельности юридическими и физическими лицами в республике.*

Ключевые слова: *инвестиции, инвестор, инвестиционная деятельность, имущество, проект, субъекты инвестиционной деятельности, инвестиционные ресурсы, капитальные вложения, инновационные инвестиции, социальные инвестиции.*

INTRODUCTION

The creation of a suitable business environment for entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, a wide system of guarantees and incentives, a suitable investment environment for foreign investors and the creation of an appropriate infrastructure that ensures the maximum economic efficiency of the funds invested by them will

significantly increase investment activity and increase the amount of capital investments directed to our economy. if not possible.

Investments play an important role in modernization of the economy, technical and technological renewal, radical change of its structural structure and diversification, ensuring high stable and proportionate economic growth. The following measures are being implemented in our country as part of the investment policy:

- speeding up the processes of establishment of industrial enterprises;
- promoting the participation of private capital in financing the construction of industrial facilities;
- improvement of the melioration condition of irrigated lands in agriculture, implementation of structural changes in the network, modernization of production, technical and technological equipment;
- further development of social infrastructure, transport and communication system, reconstruction, construction of houses based on exemplary projects in rural areas;
- implementation of investment projects with a quick return on capital funds;
- to create an opportunity for economic entities to operate freely;
- more free access to information and information related to investment activity;
- assessment of the activity of industrial enterprises.

METHOD AND RESULTS

At present, the role of innovatively filled investments is significantly increasing. It is they who contribute to the modernization of the real sector of the country's economy and the creation of a foundation of a new quality for sustainable, progressive development of the economy.

Table 1.

Structure of investments in fixed capital by sources of financing (as a percentage of the total)

№	exponential	2015	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022

1	Investments in fixed capital - total	100	100	100	100	100	100
	Including those funded by:						
2	republican budget	12.2	5.6	6.0	5.1	5.3	4.5
3	enterprises and organizations	46.1	33.0	34.8	32.7	34.8	34.0
4	population	11.4	16	18.6	20.0	20.4	20.7
5	bank loans and other borrowed funds	3.8	9.7	11.6	11.1	10.3	11.2
6	foreign investments and loans	21.7	28.3	21.5	20.4	19.3	19.8
7	off-budget funds	4.8	3.2	3.6	5.2	6.6	6.3

Investments, the money capital in which they originate and are initially provided, are limited in the same way as other economic resources. Therefore, meeting the need for investment resources and goods is one of the permanent, unsolvable problems of any economy, of all economic entities. The problem is that investments are resources for the future, and people always prefer current needs and spend resources that can improve life in the future to satisfy these needs, that is, they limit investments.

The Fund for the Reconstruction and Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a financial institution under the Cabinet of Ministers. and aimed at ensuring the implementation of investment policy implementation projects.

Today, among local scientists and specialists, there are many reasonable views on solving the problem of increasing the efficiency of investment activity.

They offer various activities that help to optimize the algorithm of organizing all investment activities, improve the quality of management in this area, increase the efficiency of regional investment programs, support enterprises that export products, and improve the activities of banks.

As the head of the BFA Scientific Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan K. Shaakra-mov noted, the consequences of the global financial and economic crisis, increased competition in global and regional markets require additional measures to improve the investment environment in the country. The author believes that it is appropriate to expand the scope of investment financing in the following order:

1. Determining the needs of the industry (enterprise) for necessary investments - for the purpose of modernization.
2. Formation of an investment program for financing sources.
3. Analysis of the composition of sources of financing investment projects (modernization programs).
4. Creating a favorable investment environment as a necessary condition

Scientists of Uzbekistan: D. E. N. Chepel S. and K. E. N. Abdunazarova N. one of the priority directions for improving the management functions of the state economy, within the framework of the investment program, is the gradual distribution of investment flows to large strategic projects with a high multiplier effect only to save the entire economy and resources. -level restriction, while increasing the share of non-state investments distributed under market conditions.

To prepare integrated regional investment programs, they are offered the following formation sequence:

- * strategic analysis of development of investment activities;
- * development of strategic directions of investment activities based on definitions of promising investment projects;
- * development of investment resources formation strategy;

* development of program measures to create a favorable environment for attracting investments to the regional economy;

According to M. Mahmudov, a senior lecturer at the University of Westminster in Tashkent city, critically evaluating the effectiveness of the current mechanism of financing programs for increasing the export potential of the main exporting enterprises, the scale and scope of the work being carried out in this direction is of great importance to the national economy. It should be recognized that it lags far behind real needs. Taking into account the completeness and limitations of the current sources of financing, it is promising to provide investment to key enterprises such as syndicated lending and bank project financing, venture, equity and grant funds, leasing, franchising, public-private partnerships, etc. introduction of methods is important.

CONCLUSION

In our opinion, in order to improve investment activities in our country, it is necessary to implement the following measures:

- taking into account that sustainable economic growth has been achieved in our republic, gradually abandoning the system of supporting long-distance networks and giving priority to the principles of economic interest in attracting investments;
- to increase the share of the elderly's funds in the structure of investments and to encourage the inclination of the elderly to accumulate;
- formation of an easy-to-use information system for foreign investors by standardizing the financial statements of enterprises in accordance with international standards;
- facilitating the attraction of bank funds as part of general investments by improving the lending mechanism;
- increasing the amount of attracting foreign investments to the processing networks of the industry.

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